

INVESTIGATION OF THE IMPACT OF STAGGER ANGLE MISTUNING ON THE UNSTEADY FLOW IN A TRANSONIC ROTOR AT A NEAR STALL CONDITION

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ABSTRACT

Mistuning within compressors refers to the breakdown of cyclic symmetry of geometry and/or flow field in the annulus. Mistuning is unavoidable in compressors, but its impact on aerodynamics has been largely ignored. With the continuous increase in design and analysis fidelity, it has reached a point to consider the impact of mistuning on compressor aerodynamics. This paper presents a numerical study of the effect of stagger angle mistuning on the unsteady flows within a transonic rotor at a near stall condition. The well-known NASA rotor 67 was used as the test case. A mistuned configuration with 0.1 degrees of alternate stagger angle mistuning was introduced. A series of steady analyses were performed first to obtain the performance characteristics of the tuned and mistuned fans. Then full annulus unsteady analyses were performed at operating points close to the numerical stall boundaries identified by the steady analyses. The unsteady flow analysis data was post-processed with a focus on the change of unsteady flow frequency and nodal diameter due to mistuning.

Keywords: Stagger angle mistuning, unsteady flows, near stall

1. INTRODUCTION

The blades of the same blade row installed in real engines are different, even though the difference might not be visible. However, most CFD analyses are conducted under the assumption of identical blade configurations, which means a deviation exists between the blade geometry used in such numerical analyses and the real one. With the increased fidelity in numerical analysis, there is a need to consider structural mistuning due to manufacturing and installation.

There are quite a few published studies about the influence of structural mistuning on aeroelasticity. Structural mistuning is primarily considered in terms of variation of blade natural frequency. Whitehead [1] and Ewins et al. [2] found that mistuning can positively influence flutter stability in most

cases. However, it will increase the amplitude of forced response, which can be eliminated or alleviated by arranging the mistuned blades in a specific way. Similar results were also obtained in other research [3][4]. Wang et al. [5] studied the effects of four intentional frequency mistuning patterns on aeroelastic stability. The results show that combining the effects of frequency offset and the destruction of periodicity by the introduction of mistuning can improve the aeroelastic stability. A more detailed review of frequency mistuning can be found in Ref. [6].

Besides the frequency mistuning, different blade stagger angles in the annulus and variations in the profile tolerance of each blade are usually considered. Sladojevic et al. [7] studied the effect of stagger angle mistuning on the natural frequency and damping using full-annulus unsteady simulations. Three different patterns (one blade mis-staggered, alternating mis-staggering, and random mis-staggering) at two operating speeds are analyzed. The results suggest that the variation of the damping in a mis-staggered structure is more sensitive to the natural frequencies when compared with the tuned system. Ekici et al. [8] investigated the effect of leading-edge blending on a loaded and an unloaded rotor. The study found that alternate blending degrades the stability of the loaded rotor, whereas it improves the stability of the unloaded rotor. Malzacher et al. [9] studied the effects of blade-to-blade stagger angle variations on the stability of a compressor cascade experimentally. The results show that mis-staggering can have a stabilizing or destabilizing effect depending strongly on the amount of mistuning. Phan et al. [10] studied the impact of stagger angle mistuning and frequency mistuning on the vibration mechanism of an oscillating cascade. The results show that the mistuned configuration tends to vibrate with the same frequency and a predominantly constant inter-blade phase angle. Vibration amplitudes of the blades vary significantly with a strong mode localization effect for the frequency mistuning. The study also found that the cascade with stagger

angle mistuning shows a stabilizing effect with a small amount of mistuning but exhibits a destabilizing effect with a large mistuning. For the concurrent stagger angle and frequency mistuning, the localization is stronger than in the standalone frequency mistuning case.

To sum up, there have been a few investigations of the effects of structural mistuning on aeroelasticity. However, very little can be found on the impact of structural mistuning on blade unsteady aerodynamics in the open literature. In this context, the effects of structural mistuning in terms of stagger angle variation on the unsteady flow behaviors around the rotor blade tip region of a transonic rotor are analyzed.

2. METHODS

The simulations presented in this context are performed by Turbostream [11], a structured multi-block steady/unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) solver running on graphics processing unit (GPU) clusters. The governing equations are shown below:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_V U dV = - \int_A C \cdot n dA + \int_A D \cdot n dA + \int_V S dV$$

where U denotes the conservative variable vector, C denotes the convective flux vector, D denotes the diffusive flux vector, S denotes the source term vector, and n is a unit vector normal to the face area dA .

For steady simulations, Turbostream uses an explicit time-stepping method; for unsteady simulations, the dual time-stepping method proposed by Jameson [12] is used. Based on the previous unsteady analyses [13] on the NASA Rotor67 transonic rotor, the Spalart-Allmaras (SA) turbulence model has good agreement with experimental results. Therefore, the SA turbulence model is used to run all simulations presented in this paper.

3. RESEARCH SUBJECT AND CFD SETUP

NASA Rotor 67, a widely used transonic fan with detailed experimental data for validating numerical results, is chosen as the subject. Firstly, a two-passage steady simulation without stagger angle mistuning is performed as a reference. The next step is to introduce staggering mistuning to these two passages: the stagger angle for one blade is increased, but for the other blade is decreased for the same amount (0.1 degrees), as shown in FIGURE 1. The unsteady simulations are conducted with a full-annulus computational domain, as shown in FIGURE 2. All meshes used in the study are generated using NUMECA/AUTOGRI5 and are of the multi-block O4H topology with an O-mesh surrounding the blade. The distance of the nearest grid point to a wall is set to 5e-6m. Based on the grid independence study [14], the grid with 2 million nodes per passage is selected to carry out all the simulations.

FIGURE 1 Schematic representation of stagger angle mistuning

Typical inlet and outlet boundary conditions (total pressure P_0 , total temperature T_0 , axial flow direction at the inlet, static pressure at the outlet p_b) are used. Solver settings are the same for all steady simulations at different operating points, and so are the unsteady simulations to make the results comparable. As the unsteady flow behaviors at near stall conditions can be sensitive to boundary conditions, a converged nozzle is applied at the outlet of the computation domain to reduce the effect of the outlet boundary conditions [14]. In this study, a converged nozzle is applied with constant back pressure at the outlet. The nozzle outlet is adjusted to achieve the throttling process.

FIGURE 2 Unsteady computational domain

Unsteady analyses at several operating points were carried out in this study. The physical time step independence study was conducted with the different time-step sizes. Fifty steps, 100 steps, and 200 steps for a rotor blade passing period are chosen to analyze the flow field at one operating point (marked as 'A' in FIGURE 5) of the tuned system. FIGURE 3 shows the mass flow difference between three different time-step sizes. The mass flow differences under different time step sizes at the same operating point are not noticeable. The frequency characteristics of the static pressure near the casing in front of the rotor blade leading edge are compared. The static pressure history and their FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) analyses are shown in FIGURE 4. Both amplitude and frequency of the major component calculated using 50 steps and 100 steps show a significant deviation, while less difference can be observed between the 100 and 200 steps. At this operating point, the frequency of the dominant unsteadiness is about 16EO, which means the number of physical time steps is about 69, 137, and 275 over

the period of the dominant unsteady flow component in three time-step configurations mentioned above. The results show that 137 steps are enough to resolve the unsteadiness. For the operating points closer to the stall boundary, the frequency of the unsteadiness reduces, which means the period is longer and the number of time steps per period is even larger. For example, at OP3 of the tuned system the frequency of the

unsteadiness is about 4EO, then the period of the unsteadiness is four times longer, which means there are 276, 552, and 1104 (much larger than the 137 steps mentioned above) physical time steps per period of unsteadiness. Therefore, considering the accuracy and computational cost, 100 steps for a rotor passing period are chosen for all unsteady simulations presented in this paper.

FIGURE 3 Mass flow differences under different time step sizes

FIGURE 4 Frequency characteristics of static pressure obtained using three different time step sizes

4. OVERALL PERFORMANCE

The performances at the design speed for both the tuned and the mistuned system are shown in FIGURE 5. With a converged nozzle applied at the outlet, the throttling process is achieved by gradually closing the converged nozzle. Two different back pressures were used: same as the inlet total

pressure and 60% of the inlet total pressure (marked as ‘more choked’ in FIGURE 5). The ‘more choked’ case is used to confirm that the different back pressure at the nozzle outlet has little influence on the results of the unsteady analyses and an operating condition is determined by the nozzle throat area. FIGURE 6 shows the axial velocity distributions at the near casing area under two different back pressure at the nozzle

outlet (the operating points with the similar mass flow). The wakes downstream of the rotor blade can be mixed fully and the flow field of these two settings are almost uniform at the inlet of the nozzle. Therefore, it can be concluded that the back pressure at the nozzle outlet will not seriously affect the unsteady analyses.

Compared with the tuned system, the mistuned system suffers a reduction in isentropic efficiency and pressure ratio. Several unsteady operating points are analyzed to find out the stall boundary. One exciting finding is that under the same step size in closing the nozzle, the mistuned system can have a wider stall boundary, this means stagger angle mistuning can expand the stable operating range of the fan rotor (with an increase of 1.82 percentage points of the stall margin). A more detailed comparison of the flow fields between the tuned and the mistuned system is then carried out to investigate the effect of the stagger angle mistuning on the unsteady flow behaviors at the near stall point.

FIGURE 5 Performance maps at the design speed

(a) Back pressure: 1.0*inlet total pressure

(b) Back pressure: 0.6*inlet total pressure
FIGURE 6 Axial velocity distribution with different back pressure at the nozzle outlet

5. SPATIAL and TEMPORAL CHARACTERISTICS

The unsteady flow behaviors of the tuned system and the mistuned system at near stall conditions are analyzed. Based on the previous analyses of this case [14], three unsteady operating points for the tuned system are chosen as a reference for the mistuned system. FIGURE 7 shows the axial velocity distribution near the casing at the first unsteady operating point (marked as ‘A’ in FIGURE 5) of the tuned system. The red line refers to the axial locations of the numerical probes, which are set in front of each blade leading edge for analyzing the characteristics of the unsteady flows. In FIGURE 7, spillage of the leakage flow with one nodal diameter initiated from the blade leading edge can be observed. The frequency characteristics and nodal diameters of this unsteady flow are different at different operating points, which are thought to be the precursor for rotating stalls. Therefore, if one wants to postpone or avoid rotating stalls, there is a need to suppress the unsteady flows near the blade tip.

Three operating points of the mistuned system with similar mass flow rates as the tuned system are chosen to compare the unsteady flow behaviors. FIGURE 8 shows the axial velocity distributions near the casing for the tuned and mistuned systems. The upper three plots are for the tuned system, with a decreasing mass flow from left to right; the lower three plots are for the mistuned system, with a decreasing mass flow from left to right. For the tuned system, as the operating point gets closer to the stall boundary, more circumferential waves can be observed, which means the number of circumferential disturbances increases. Based on the previous study, these circumferential disturbances can be seen as rotating stall

precursors [14]. When the compressor is further pushed to the stall boundary, one of the disturbances will expand and develop into a rotating stall cell. While for the mistuned system, during the throttling process, the number of the circumferential disturbances is always 11, which is related to the alternate stagger angle mistuning (the blade count is 22). By contrasting the unsteady flows of these two configurations, the unsteady flow pattern near the blade tip of the tuned system can freely develop, while the unsteady flow pattern of the mistuned system is restricted by the alternate stagger angle mistuning. Therefore, one can introduce a proper level of intentional mistuning configuration to design the unsteady flow pattern near the blade tip so as to suppress some destructive unsteady flows within the tuned system.

FIGURE 7 Axial velocity distributions near the casing at the first unsteady operating point of the tuned system

The numerical probes are set at the same location for all unsteady operating points, as shown in FIGURE 7. FIGURE 9 shows the static pressure histories recorded by the numerical probes for the same operating points in FIGURE 8. The red lines in the upper three plots are for the static pressure from a reference passage of the tuned system, while the black lines are the shifted signals from other passages. The red lines in the lower three plots are the static pressure from the two adjacent reference passages, and the black lines are also the shifted signals from other passages. When the operating point gets closer to the stall boundary, larger oscillation amplitudes are observed (from left to right). For the mistuned system (lower three plots in FIGURE 9), the differences between the nearby passages also expand with the operating point getting closer to the stall boundary. When comparing the tuned system with the mistuned system, the oscillation amplitudes of the static pressure around the blades with increased stagger angle decreases, while an increase is observed around the blades with reduced stagger angle. Also, there is a phase difference between the static pressures from different passages in the tuned system. While for the mistuned system, the phase angles of the static pressure from different passages with the same stagger angle (the passages with increased or reduced stagger angle) are all the same and are opposite to those of their nearby passages. This characteristic results from the alternate mistuning pattern, leading to 11 nodal diameters.

FIGURE 8 Axial velocity distributions near the casing for the tuned and mistuned systems at three different operating points

FIGURE 9 Static pressure histories from different numerical probes

To determine the frequency characteristics of the unsteady disturbances, FFT analyses were performed on the static pressure recorded by the numerical probes, with results shown in FIGURE 10. For the tuned system (FIGURE 10 (a)), the amplitude of the disturbances is significantly increased from operating point 1 to operating point 3. The difference in the frequencies at the three operating points in the tuned system is due to the decrease in the rotating speed and the increase in the nodal diameter of the disturbances. For the mistuned system (FIGURE 10 (b)), the amplitudes of the disturbances from two neighboring blades at each operating point show a significant difference: the unsteadiness around the blades with reduced stagger angle is increased but the unsteadiness around the blades with increased stagger angle are suppressed. It can also be noticed that the averaged amplitudes of the disturbances (from two nearby passages) in the mistuned system are almost the same as the tuned system. When the operating point is gradually getting closer to the stall point, the frequency of disturbance does not vary a lot.

To conclude, the nodal diameter and frequency of the disturbances in the mistuned system almost keep unchanged and the amplitude increases when the operating point moves closer to the stall point. In other words, the alternate stagger angle mistuning can suppress the variation of nodal diameters and frequencies of unsteady flows during the throttling process.

(a) the tuned system

(b) the mistuned system

FIGURE 10 Spectral analysis results of the static pressure histories

6. STALL CHARACTERISTICS

Based on the operating point 3 shown in FIGURE 9, the nozzle outlet is further closed. The tuned system will develop a rotating stall first, and the axial velocity histories from the numerical probes are shown in FIGURE 11. During this process, one disturbance in the circumferential direction firstly expands to other passages, which finally leads to the rotating stall. More details about the rotating stall in the tuned system can be found in Ref. [14].

FIGURE 11 Axial velocity histories during the rotating stall in the tuned system

The stall behaviors in the mistuned system are more concerned in this paper. FIGURE 12 shows the axial velocity histories during the stall process in the mistuned system. The major difference is that the phase angles from different passages with the same stagger angle keep the same, which means the size of disturbances does not expand in the circumferential direction. FIGURE 13 shows the wavelet

analyses of the axial velocity from the numerical probes in the tuned (FIGURE 13 (a)) and mistuned (FIGURE 13 (b)) systems. The typical rotating stall is found in the tuned system, however, the frequency of the unsteady flows in the mistuned system almost keeps constant. Finally, both the tuned system and the mistuned system will numerically diverge.

FIGURE 12 Axial velocity histories during the rotating stall in the mistuned system

FIGURE 13 Wavelet analyses for the axial velocity at the last unsteady operating point

7. CONCLUSION

NASA rotor 67 has been used to numerically investigate the influence of alternate stagger angle mistuning on unsteady flow characteristics. First steady analyses using two blade passages were carried out to obtain the speedlines of the original fan and an alternate-stagger-angle-mistuned fan at the design speed. Then full annulus unsteady analyses were carried out at operating points close to the numerical stall boundaries identified by the steady analyses to investigate the change of unsteady flow frequency and circumferential nodal diameter and their response to a throttling process due to mistuning. The following conclusions can be drawn.

1. Appropriate level (0.1 degrees in this study) of alternate stagger angle mistuning can expand the

stall boundary of a transonic compressor at the expense of a slight reduction of efficiency and pressure ratio.

2. Intentional stagger angle mistuning can be introduced to control the unsteady flow modes near the casing; in other words, the disturbances with an undesired nodal diameter can be altered this way.
3. With the alternate stagger angle mistuning, the amplitude of the unsteady flows near the casing around the blades with increased stagger angle decreases while the amplitude around the blades with reduced stagger angle increases, which can lead to the expansion of the stall boundary.

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